

PaNET ontology

Sustainability sheet

The PaNET ontology provides a taxonomy of **experimental techniques** relevant for the Photon and Neutron community.

Currently, experimental techniques are often described using a natural language in some plain text description field. To make discovery easier, PaNET allows a **unique and unambiguous** description of the experimental technique(s) to be added to **datasets** (and related research objects) in order to document how the material was created. It may also be used to tag many other items; for example, **training material**, analysis services, analysis workflows, analysis software, workshops.

	Target audiences	Benefits
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Instrument scientists- Data stewards- Data managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Use a common set of standard technique names- Be able to refer to global persistent identifiers- Ease interoperability of data catalogues and search across facilities- Enrich search results with subclasses and alternative labels
	Accessibility	Documentation
	Ontology can be browsed in BioPortal (1) or in the documentation (2) Source code (3) The persistent URL service is used, which redirects terms to their definition.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Methodology (4)- Ontology (2)
	Feedback mechanism	Licence CC BY 4.0 (5)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Monthly meeting of PaNET developers and contributors - in the future, possibly including data stewards of each facility- GitHub issue tracking (6) used to request new terms or indicate problems with existing terms- Review process and release defined and taking place in the github repo (7)	
	Competitors	
	Wikidata contains entries for several experimental techniques (8)	
	Technology readiness	
	In production	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Used in the federated PaN search API via the ontology service, which (in turn) is used by the PaNOSC search portal (9)- Used in the PaN training platform (10)- Used at Diamond to categorise publications	
	EOSC integration status	
	A production instance of the ontology service , provided by PSI has been on-boarded (11)	

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Plans and conditions for long-term sustainability

- Will continue to be hosted in [GitHub.com](https://github.com) (4), likely under a different organisation
- Core team of five individuals from four institutes who are meeting once a month to discuss the maintenance of PaNET, meeting that will continue after ExPaNDS end
- Initial version of the release process is documented

Exploitability potential

- PaN search API could enrich its results using PaNET
- PaN-training catalogue and E-learning platform to use PaNET to control the vocabulary used for tags
- Embedding PaNET terms within files (e.g., NeXus) and metadata catalogues
- Use PaNET terms in user-office systems (within proposals)
- Use PaNET terms to describe publications
- There may be interest within national projects; e.g the [DAPHNE4NFDI project](#) (12)
- [Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration](#) (13) has also expressed interest in supporting PaNET
- There may also be interest in science domain specific communities; e.g., EOSC-Life/ELIXIR, to be explored in the frame of the upcoming OSCARS project

Conditions to increase exploitability

Various actions to increase visibility and exploitability have been opened as Github issues:

- [PaNET issue #75 Register PaNET with ontology catalogues](#) (14)
- [PaNET issue #63 Including PaNET within a NeXus file?](#) (15)

Links

- (1) <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/PANET>
- (2) <http://purl.org/pan-science/PaNET/>
- (3) <https://github.com/ExPaNDS-eu/ExPaNDS-experimental-techniques-ontology>
- (4) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4806026>
- (5) <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>
- (6) <https://github.com/ExPaNDS-eu/ExPaNDS-experimental-techniques-ontology/issues>
- (7) <https://github.com/ExPaNDS-eu/ExPaNDS-experimental-techniques-ontology#review-process-and-release>
- (8) For example: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q1000635>
- (9) <https://data.panosc.eu/>
- (10) <https://pan-training.eu/>
- (11) <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/photon-and-neutron-techniques-ontology-service>
- (12) <https://www.daphne4nfdi.de/english/index.php>
- (13) <https://helmholtz-metadaten.de/en>
- (14) <https://github.com/ExPaNDS-eu/ExPaNDS-experimental-techniques-ontology/issues/75>
- (15) <https://github.com/ExPaNDS-eu/ExPaNDS-experimental-techniques-ontology/issues/63>

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